

Table 1. The competencies developed during the workshop

(A) Macro-competencies and description (Quelhas <i>et al.</i> , 2019): ability to...	(B) Competence and description: ability to...	(C) How is it developed in the workshop?
Critical thinking - Question norms, practices and opinions.	(1) Question design indicators. (2) Question the current way of designing in a company. (3) Question company practices.	Value Analysis raises the question of design indicators: "traditional" indicators (functions/costs) vs an approach based on the donut. The donut is used as a support to determine the relevant indicators and even a weighting.
Working in an interdisciplinary group - Manage conflict, to always seek collaboration and participation in problem-solving and to seek relationships, understanding and sensitivity towards team members (empathic leadership).	(4) Exchange ideas between workshop participants. (5) Co-construct design indicators. (6) Listen to participants' opinions and incorporate them into the search for indicators.	People must understand and speak each other. The Doughnut is used as a support for exchanges. Applied to design, the Doughnut enables global skills to be mobilised regarding social and ecological dimensions in a context. These dimensions meet the various aspects of Sustainability, which requires interdisciplinarity.
Problem-solving - Solve complex sustainability problems and develop viable, inclusive and equitable solutions that promote sustainability	(7) Propose a solution in response to the problem posed, i.e. how can sustainability issues be taken into account in the design? (8) Take stakeholders' expectations into account.	The results of the workshop show whether the problem posed has been solved AND justified (Is there a choice of bicycle that is supported (method, calculations, etc.)?)
Systemic thinking - Identify and understand the interactions between systems and people in the social, cultural, environmental (..) contexts in which they operate.	(9) Identify the stakeholders in relation to the designed object. (10) Relate stakeholders to planetary limits and the social floor. (11) Relate planetary limits and the social floor to the design object.	Can they make the link between the bike that is designed and the different limits and thresholds? Can they make a link between each limit and threshold (between themselves and between limits and thresholds)?
Normative competence - Understand and reflect on the norms and values that underpin people's actions, and to negotiate the values, principles, objectives and goals of sustainability in a context of conflicting interests, concessions and contradictions.	(12) Identify participants' values. (13) Take account of stakeholders' values/expectations. (14) Negotiate with participants to take account of all the planetary limits and the social floor.	Does the group manage to take into account the point of view of the various stakeholders (input data) and to differentiate between their own feelings and those of the stakeholders?
Self-awareness - Reflect on one's own role in the local community and society, to constantly evaluate one's own actions and to manage one's own feelings and desires.	(15) Step back from one's actions during the workshop. (16) Integrate elements in their job. (17) Question one's role in society. (18) Question the role of the engineer within the company.	Taking a step back from oneself: do the participants manage to realise their bias(s) during the workshop
Contextualisation and vision of the future - Understand why certain knowledge and skills are needed to visualise solutions and consequences in a wider context	Competence not assessed	The time devoted to this training only provides an introduction to the challenges of sustainability.
Strategic competence - Collectively develop and implement innovative actions to promote sustainability at local/global level.	Competence not assessed	This is a workshop in which the exercise is too rigid for participants to develop this competence.